

THE ROL OF TEACHERS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the teacher's ability to engage in foreign language classes in professional educational institutions and various methods. Also, the article provides information about ways to interest students in the organization of lessons based on modern technologies.*

Keywords: *pedagogue, leader, pedagogical experience, pedagogical technology, modern approach, listening, writing, speaking, self study.*

"Ignorance is better than having little knowledge"

(Abu Ali Ibn Sina)

INTRODUCTION

A person who aims to learn a field involuntarily feels the need for a teacher. This is clearly visible in the field of languages. A student who wants to learn a new language does not know where to start. At that time, the teacher guides the student. The original meaning of the word teacher - pedagogue means "one who follows the child on the way, leads the child". If we turn to the long history of pedagogues, even in the Greek states, which were the home of philosophers, teachers were respected among the people through their knowledge and experience. Teachers were respected not only by students, but also by their parents. Since there were not enough conditions for education in those times and it was very difficult to get an apprenticeship, the students who were studying also considered the education given by pedagogues and pedagogues to be the possessors of inexhaustible knowledge.

Today, every field is developing and new things are coming. And because of this, foreign languages, especially English, have taken an important place, as well as mother tongue, history and other subjects. Today, 50% of 60% of young people in Uzbekistan choose English as a foreign language and can see a promising future in this language. Among them, we can find many people who have obtained international foreign language proficiency certificates, that is, IELTS, TOEFL or MULTI LEVEL national certificates. Of course, the pedagogic experiences and methods of knowledgeable teachers contribute to the achievement of such victories by today's youth. It should also be noted that acquiring knowledge and following the path of knowledge is not easy for everyone. For this, a clear goal, attention and a determined approach are required from the student. Also, the reforms implemented in our country to improve the quality of education are showing their results. In particular, among 17-18-year-old students in vocational schools, there are only a few who eagerly learn foreign languages by heart. It was also emphasized by our honorable president that students graduating from schools should master at least two foreign languages perfectly.

In order to learn foreign languages and popularize it, the decision of the President of May 19, 2021 No. PQ-5117 was adopted. In accordance with the state program "Year of youth support and population health promotion", development of foreign language learning as a priority direction

of education policy, radical improvement of education quality in this direction, attracting qualified pedagogues to the field and in order to increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages:

- to popularize the study of foreign languages among the population and create the necessary conditions for their perfect mastery, coordination of the introduction of internationally recognized programs and textbooks of foreign language teaching at all stages of education, and modern teaching skills in teachers development;

- organizing training of foreign languages in high demand based on the results of the analysis of the needs of regional networks and educational institutions for specialists who have mastered foreign languages;

- to develop methodologies and recommendations for language learning suitable for all levels of the population in order to introduce a continuous educational chain on the principle of "kindergarten - school - higher education organization - enterprise" in the field of foreign language teaching coordination;

organizing the creation of videos, games, entertainment shows, films and other educational content for the thorough mastery of foreign languages, the formation of basic language skills; - creation of professional translation methods from the state language to foreign languages and from foreign languages to the state language and assistance in improving the qualifications of specialists in this direction;

- maintaining the rating of knowledge of foreign languages in terms of regions, sectors, state bodies and educational organizations, developing proposals for further popularizing the study of foreign languages. In order to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages:

From September 1, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan prize was established in order to encourage schools that have achieved the best results in teaching foreign languages; - The Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, governors of the regions and the city of Tashkent have launched a practice of allocating a one-time subsidy of up to 50 million soums from local budget funds to business entities for the organization of foreign language teaching activities in rural areas; - the practice of paying an additional monthly bonus of 50% of the basic tariff rate to teachers of foreign languages with an internationally recognized certificate of at least C1 level or an equivalent level was implemented.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The main purpose of such decisions is, of course, to create more opportunities for the youth and the population. If we look at paragraph 3 of this decision, in order to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages and to encourage students, even the President's award was established. And not only students, but also teachers are not left out of this privilege. If we look at paragraph 5 of the decision, foreign language teachers who have received a national or international C1 level certificate in a foreign language will receive a monthly bonus of 50%. So, today teachers have enough conditions to work on themselves and teach using advanced pedagogical technologies, even in the most remote areas.

True, today it is possible to find all the necessary information on the Internet, and this is a very effective method for those who choose the path of "independent learning". However, sometimes when it is difficult to find reliable information, the teacher acts as a guide. On the other hand, some students need a teacher's encouragement and guidance. Now foreign languages are being taught to elementary school students in schools. At this time, the child's interest in English

depends on the teacher. It is not for nothing that the saying "Knowledge acquired in youth is like a pattern carved in stone" appeared in our nation. But even young children, students of public education and professional education schools, do not completely abandon the character of playfulness depending on their age. According to Japanese writer Ibuka Masaro's book "It's Late After Three", a child can be taught up to three foreign languages by the age of three, and this has been scientifically proven. Any new science, new direction, which is intended to be studied, requires time, practice and patience. Therefore, more responsibility is assigned to the teacher. As time progressed, the traditional way of teaching became untenable. The extent to which a student is interested in a field depends primarily on the interesting lessons and the teacher who makes the lesson interesting.

Currently, in learning any foreign language, great attention is paid to the development of reading, listening, writing and speaking skills. To be the best at these four skills, you must first have sufficient basic and general knowledge skills. For example, we can say that the book "English Grammar" by Muhammad Gaffarov and Robiya Kasimova is perfect for improving general English grammar for young people studying in professional educational institutions. Also, the books "Essential Grammar in Use 1", "Essential Grammar in Use 2" by Cambridge University professor Raymond Murphy and "English Grammar in Practice" by Uzbek linguist F.V. Rahmatov are the best books for strengthening knowledge skills through exercises. books help a lot.

It is clear that any student will get bored if he only deals with one area of the language during the lessons. For example, 15-20 minutes of listening comprehension for 80 minutes will be enough. Or, in order to better remember high-level words used in written speech, only teachers can understand and convey to their students how to use them in oral speech situations. Or just a few important points for mastering the "reading and understanding" direction of reading. Students face a lot of difficulties when they start working with reading, and reading becomes an unpleasant activity for them. In such a situation, the responsibility of guiding students in the right way falls on the teacher. To improve reading ability, first of all, it is necessary to pay great attention to the wealth of vocabulary. In order to remember the dictionary well, the most effective way is not to memorize a single word, but to memorize it together with related words. For example, beautiful - beautiful, a beautiful girl - a beautiful girl. In addition, another tried-and-tested method for memorizing vocabulary is to memorize words that have the same root but have different meanings at the same time. For example, nation - nation, national - national, nationalism - freedom fighter, nationalistic - nationalist, nationalization - nationalization, etc.

RESULTS

Memorizing words with the help of combinations will greatly help to translate reading easier and faster. When learning a new language, all students mainly face difficulties and misunderstandings in vocabulary memorization. Frankly speaking, the biggest shortcoming is related to the glossary part of the new language. Language learners are recommended to start adapting to such a challenge in advance. And IELTS instructors say that giving love to reading helps not only the development of reading, but also the listening and writing skills to achieve high scores. And in combination with functional and semantic support, which contributes to the development of writing skills and the ability to make sufficiently detailed statements aimed at the use of certain language materials, the game also gives the most accurate results.

CONCLUSION

Vocational school students are 17-18-year-old boys and girls, each of whom needs special attention and encouragement. It must be admitted that regardless of age, if the work started is warmly received by others, the self-confidence of the performer increases. The inner world of the student, along with his behavior, the profession he wants to take or the direction he is interested in, is also an area that needs attention from the teacher. In the course of the lesson, foreign language teachers not only teach in the traditional way, but also "Warm-up" games or "Quick questions" that serve to help the students to gather their imaginations faster without straying away from the language being studied even when they are bored. It will be appropriate if he uses "answer" methods. And it should be noted that teachers of foreign languages divide one class into two groups and engage in lessons. If we assume that 15 students attend the class in one group, one teacher should give tasks to each of those 15 children for 80 minutes and answer oral questions. If should also evaluate it for motivation, even if mistakes and shortcomings are made by the students during the training, it should be explained to the students 5 minutes before the break and it should also be evaluated appropriately.

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